

Study of density of states and minimum hopping distance of $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_2\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_9$ ferroelectric nanoceramics prepared by precursor solution decomposition method

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Manuscript received 13 August 2018, accepted 23 August 2018

Nanocrystalline layered perovskite $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_2\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_9$ (BNiBN) ferroelectric ceramics is synthesized using precursor solution decomposition method. The ceramics have tolerance factor 0.85 which is well within its limit. The binding energy is calculated from the ac conductivity slope characteristics. The conductivity study successfully establishes the correlated barrier hopping (CBH) model. The minimum hopping distance increases and density of states decreases with increasing frequency.

Keywords: Layered perovskite, tolerance factor, binding energy, density of states, minimum hopping distance.

Introduction

Lead based ferroelectrics materials like lead zirconium titanate (PZT), lead magnesium niobate-lead titanate (PMN-PT), lead magnesium niobate (PMN), lead zinc niobate (PZN) are most important due to their applications in STM/AFM actuators, sensors, ultra sound transducers, fuel injectors, ferroelectric random access memories (FRAM) chips etc.¹. But the presence of toxic lead in these ferroelectric materials leads to the environmental issue and prohibited throughout the world². Again there are some disadvantages of PZT like polarization loss with switching cycles on Pt electrodes³. So, lead free ferroelectrics materials with comparable properties are important to the researchers. In this sense bismuth layered structured ferroelectrics (BLSFs) are more important. Aurivillius first reported this type of compounds around 68 years ago⁴. The general formula of Aurivillius compound is $[\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2]^{2+}[\text{A}_{m-1}\text{B}_m\text{O}_{3m+1}]^{2-}$ where pseudo-perovskite blocks of $[\text{A}_{m-1}\text{B}_m\text{O}_{3m+1}]^{2-}$ are sandwiched between two $[\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2]^{2+}$ layers. The 'A' position is 12 fold coordination sites that occupied by mono, di, or trivalent ions; 'B' site that octahedrally coordinated by oxygen ions occupied by tetravalent, pentavalent or hexavalent ions and 'm' indicates the number of corner that sharing BO_6 octahedra. BLSFs with $m = 2$ are most important to the scientists due to their attractive properties like low operating voltage, excellent switching speed, small leakage current density etc.

Among them $\text{BaBi}_2\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_9$ (BBN) is one of the most im-

portant material due to its relaxor behaviour⁵. The details X-ray and neutron diffraction study show that Ba is incorporated into the Bi-layers that lead to the imbalance in layered structure⁶. This imbalance in layer structure probably leads to the diffuseness of the phase formation that causes the relaxor behavior of the material. Relaxor behavior of the materials is important as they have exceptionally high dielectric and piezoelectric responses over a wide range of temperatures⁷. Kholkin *et al.* showed that BBN exhibited relaxor behavior and ΔT_{max} is over 100 K between 1 kHz and 1 MHz⁸. Though due to the higher processing temperature, higher dc resistivity, lower remnant polarizations of the relaxor materials⁹ they should be modified by doping. Phadtare *et al.* substitute Ba^{2+} in place of Ca^{2+} in $\text{CaBi}_2\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_9$ and exhibited that with increasing the Ba^{2+} concentration the remnant polarization increases gradually¹⁰. Badapanda *et al.* study the high density of states of $(\text{Ba}_{1-x}\text{Bi}_{2x/3}\text{Zr}_{0.25}\text{Ti}_{0.75}\text{O}_3)$ ($x = 0.025$) (BBZT) ceramic due to the hopping between the pair of sites and correlated barrier hopping (CBH) model is successfully explained¹¹. Substitution of transition metal ions at the 'A' site gives the good characteristics of relaxor as well as density of states, hopping behavior etc. which are discussed in our previous study¹²⁻¹⁶.

In our present study we chose the transition metal ion Ni^{2+} for the substitution at the 'A' site of BBN. The size of the metal ion is very small than the ionic radius Ba^{2+} that leads to the free space of BO_6 octahedra resulting diffused phase

transition. Again Jahn-Teller distortion of the metal enhances the distortion¹². According to the researchers the interior defects like 'A' site vacancies, space charge electrons, and oxygen vacancies have great influence in ferroelectric, fatigue and ionic conductivity^{17,18}. Here, we discuss about the density of states and hopping behavior of $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_2\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_9$.

Experimental

Crystalline $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_2\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_9$ (BNiBN) nanoceramic is prepared using chemical precursor solution decomposition method. The starting materials for the synthesis are $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (Merck, India, $\geq 99\%$), $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (Merck, India, $\geq 99\%$), $\text{Bi}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ (Aldrich, 99.999%), Nb-tartarate (prepared from Nb_2O_5 (Aldrich, 99.99%)), triethanol amine (Merck, India $\geq 99\%$), tartaric acid (Loba Chemie, India, 99.5%), HNO_3 (Merck, India, GR grade), NH_4OH (Merck, India, GR grade). The synthesis procedure is already described in our previous publication¹⁵. Fig. 1 represents the synthesis procedure of BNiBN.

The materials characterizations are done using X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) study (Bruker D8 Advance eco), Fourier Transform Infra Red spectroscopy (FTIR) study (Perkin-Elmer Spectrum Two), Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) (SEM, Jeol JSM5800) and Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectroscopy study. For the electrical characterization the powder sample is mixed with 5% polyvinyl alcohol and form a pellet using a hydraulic press. The pellet is sintered at 750°C

for 4 h. Then the pellet is silver coated both side using silver paste, dried at 180°C for 2 h and then used for electrical characterization. HIOKI LCR HITESTER (Japan, Model No. 3532-50) is used for the electrical measurements.

Results and discussion

The XRD, FTIR, SEM and EDX analyses are done in our previous publication¹⁵. The XRD study shows that the ceramics have single phase orthorhombic structure. The tolerance factor for BNiBN is calculated using the following equation^{19,20}.

$$t = \frac{\langle r_A \rangle + r_O}{\sqrt{2}(r_B + r_O)}$$

where r_A and r_O are the average ionic radius of 'A' site cations and radius of the oxide ion respectively and r_B is the radius of 'B' site cation. The tolerance factor of BNiBN is 0.85 that indicated the samples have lower symmetrical structure¹¹. According to Karthik *et al.* the tolerance factor for a perovskite structure is in between 0.80 and 1.10¹⁹.

Thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA) of the precursor mass is done using thermo gravimetric analyzer (Perkin-Elmer STA 6000). The heating rate during this procedure is $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ in nitrogen gas atmosphere up to 800°C . The plot of loss of weight in percentage vs temperature is shown in Fig. 2. A significant weight loss, more than 50% is observed in the material. This is due to the evaporation of solvent, decomposition and decarbonization of organic and inorganic com-

Fig. 1. Flowchart diagram for the preparation of $\text{Ba}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Bi}_2\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_9$ (BNiBN).

Fig. 2. Thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA) plot of precursor mass of BNiBN ceramic.

pounds. Above 650°C there is no change of the sample weight.

The theory of ac conductivity is first established by Pollak and Gaballe in 1961²¹, it is then modified by Austin and Mott²² and described the transport process of amorphous semiconductor with defect states. The frequency dependence ac conductivity obeys the following Jonscher's power law equation²³.

$$\sigma(\omega) = \sigma_{dc} + A\omega^n$$

where the value of n is $0 < n < 1$. 'A' and 'n' are thermally activated quantities. At the low temperature region the materials obey $\sigma(\omega) \propto \omega^n$.

According to the CBH model the binding energy of BNiBN is calculated using the following relationship²⁴.

$$\beta = \frac{6k_B T}{W_m}$$

Here, $\beta = 1 - n$, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the temperature and W_m is the binding energy. The binding energy of an electron is defined as the energy required removing an electron from one site to another site. The plot of slope and binding energy vs temperature is given in Fig. 3. The Fig. 3 indicated the slope value decreases with increasing temperature up to 460°C then it rises and the binding energy follow the same path. The decrease of slope with rising temperature is due to the decreasing binding energy. At high temperature i.e. above 460°C the ac conductivity increases rapidly that effects the slope characteristics and binding energy.

The minimum hopping distance (R_{min}) i.e. the minimum

Fig. 3. Slope and binding energy vs temperature plot of BNiBN ceramic.

distance in which the electrons hop is calculated using the following relationship²⁵.

$$R_{min} = \frac{2e^2}{\pi\epsilon_0\epsilon W_m}$$

Here ϵ_0 is the permittivity of the free space and ϵ is the dielectric constant of the material. The R_{min} vs frequency plot at different temperatures are given in Fig. 4. At different temperatures the R_{min} increases with increasing frequency. R_{min} is highest for 460°C at high frequency and at low frequency the highest R_{min} is observed at low temperature for BNiBN sample.

Fig. 4. Minimum hopping distance vs frequency plot at different temperatures.

The ac conductivity behaviour at different frequencies has three characteristic regions. At high frequency the higher conductivity observed as the transport is dominated from the contribution from hopping in the finite clusters. At mid frequency the constant conductivity due to the charge transport takes place via infinite percolation path and at low frequency the conductivity is disturbed¹¹.

In statistical and condensed matter physics, the density of states of a system indicates the number of states at each energy level that are accessible to be occupied. The density of states ($N(E_f)$) of BNiBN from ac conductivity is calculated using the following relationship²².

$$\sigma_{ac} = \frac{\pi}{3} e^2 \omega k_B T (N(E_f))^2 \alpha^{-5} \left(\ln \frac{f_0}{\omega} \right)^4$$

here ' e ' is the charge of electron, f_0 is the photon frequency and α is the localized wave function assuming $f_0 = 10^{13}$ Hz and $\alpha = 10^{10}$ m⁻¹. The $N(E_f)$ vs frequency at different temperatures is given in Fig. 5. The density of states increases with increasing temperature but with increasing frequency it decreases and merges at high frequency region.

Fig. 5. Density of states vs frequency plot at different temperatures.

Conclusions

The nanocrystalline Ba_{0.5}Ni_{0.5}Bi₂Nb₂O₉ is prepared using precursor solution decomposition method. The tolerance factor is 0.85 indicated the lower symmetrical structure. The binding energy and the slope value decreases with increasing temperature up to 460°C. The CBH model successfully explained the universal behavior of the exponent. R_{\min} is highest for 460°C at high frequency and at low frequency the highest R_{\min} is observed at low temperature for BNiBN sample. The minimum hopping distance increases and density of states decreases with increasing frequency.

Acknowledgements

Author thanks SERB, DST, New Delhi, India for financial support (Grant No. SR/FT-CS-125, 2010). Author also thanks WB DST, Govt. of West Bengal, India (Grant No. 674(Sanc)/ST/P/ S&T/15G/5/ 2016 dated 09/11/2016) for financial support. MKA is thankful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), Government of India for the Senior Research Fellowship [Sanction No. 09/1156(0004)/18-EMR-].

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